

Explore the Influence of Social Media on Social Commerce: An Empirical Study of Entrepreneurs in Chittoor District

¹Dr. G. Somasekhar, ² Dr. K. Srinivasa Krishna & ³ Dr. K. V. Geetha Devi

^{1,2,3}Assistant Professor MITS School of Business Madanapalle Institute of Technology & Science Madanapalle (India)

ARTICLE DETAILS

Article History

Published Online: 09 March 2019

Keywords

Social Media, Social Commerce, Influence, Attention, Entrepreneur

*Corresponding Author

Email: g.somasekhar.mba[at]gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Social media gained the immense popularity in global era and it generates the opportunities to the budding entrepreneurs. The substantial use of social media not only creates the opportunities for strengthening, wide unfold of the entrepreneurial business and it also acts as tool to advertise their products globally to draw the attention of numerous viewers, in order to make them to buy the product. In 21st century it became a part and parcel of their life to educate the entrepreneur to find the opportunities to secure the significant of a market share in terms of sales as well as ROI. However, there is a dearth of studies on social commerce in India, very particular how its effects on business interaction. Hence the researcher made a modest effort to explore the influence of social media on social commerce in Chittoor district.

1. Introduction

Social media has become a significant mode of communication in everybody's life, mainly among students, academicians, practitioners and entrepreneurs. Almost many of the people and entrepreneurs across the globe are sharing their day to day activities, market information and information regard different activities through social media (Kirschner and Karpinski, 2010). Marketers are persistently hunting down firm establishment to base their key choices and to influence the customers through social media and it continuously gain the popularity in the minds of people (Hoffman and Novak, 2012). According to (Chen, Fay and Wang, 2011) firms are rather to call them and they find the place to interact with more members of friends, relatives and as well as well-wishers to share their experiences in order to take the embedded decision for purchase. The firms are interacting and share their information regarding products and services for their customers and new people through social media, in turn sales are increasing. In addition, social media provides a platform for all people across anywhere in the world regard personal evaluation of purchasing products and at the same time it facilitates word of mouth communication between people. According to the view of (Stephen and Toubia, 2010) on social media networking sites, the firm and entrepreneurs are enjoying with massive number of viewers' experiences along with their business volume. In the view of (Zimmerman and Ng, 2012) social media channelize, information and promoting the firm's products & services at the lowest cost. Meanwhile, many firms are influenced by social media due to popularity among consumers. The majority of the previous studies are not much focused on social commerce side of social media, particularly among the entrepreneurs. Hence, the paper aims to 'explore the influence of social media on social commerce in Chittoor district among various entrepreneurs.

2. Literature Review

Social media & Social network sites

Many of the peoples are sharing their opinions, thoughts, communications and exchanging information through social

media networking sites. Hence social media is a channel for social interaction among the individuals (Ahlqvist et al., 2008). It is well-stricken thought focus on one-to many communication techniques. It has been derived from "a cluster of Internet-based applications that rely on the ideologies and technological foundations of web 2.0 which allows the creation and exchange of user generated content". The people are sharing their wider interests, ideas' swap, regular updates of postings and comments, involving activities & events (Kaplan and Haenlein, 2010). Faceto face conversations and encouraging transactions by broadening the sophisticated technology (Moran et al., 2011). Social media encourages or allows many of the people follows important news, maintaining the relations with friends or colleagues and invite online debates from intellectual people from different places. However, social networking focuses a great deal of engagements, which builds the relationship, communication networks with reader, followers, and draws the attention online viewers (Kirschner and Karpinski, 2010). According to (ITU, 2010) experts mention that social media will be a new search platform, anticipated that individuals are paying less attention instead the people are searching the information from their friends and maintain word of mouth interactions to take decisions; this is called "friend-casting". (Davis et al., 2014 & Marsden, 2011) study highlights that many of the individuals are extensively using Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Skype, WhatsApp and Instagram in their daily lives. (Info graphic, 2014) report reveals that over 700 million users accessed Facebook from 7000 different devices, more than five hundred million users accessed Twitter, and over one hundred thirty million used Instagram in 2013. In present days the individuals are going through the different social media or networking sites on every day to obtain the information to meet their intentions. Past research report reveal that Facebook users check their account five times in a day, getting thousands of responses per second on Twitter. Moreover, receiving five million photos and videos being shared in twenty-four hours via through Instagram. Hence, these social media channels become the part of their life style and edutainers (Boyd, 2007; Boyd and Ellison, 2007; Nicholson, 2011). (Turban et al., 2012) reveals that there is tremendous popularity increases drastically of aforesaid social media channels and these are

provided opened opportunities for starting new business models with the e-commerce in other words social commerce (S-Commerce). According to (Hussain & Bohari, 2012) online business makes use of it on a convenient base for the development of business due to growth in high-speed of internet connection.

Literature on Electronic and Social commerce

Nearly by century Electronic commerce was existed; however, the term electronic commerce has seemed as a key topic, within the literature, meanwhile the web started to be used commercially in the Nineties and significantly used by business and management areas (Zwass, 1996). Most of the studies from across the globe highlights that e-commerce not an adoption and moreover it's a phenomenon (Hashim and Abdullah, 2014). (Wang and Zhang, 2012) in his study mentioned that the results of electronic commerce across the countries are unlimited, some companies are already starting their business through e-commerce and others are still at the beginning stage. The study also pointed out that s-commerce would be a subset of electronic commerce that focuses on utilization of social, online media that provide social communication and helps online shopping for products and services. Many of the firms are counting their customers through rising trends in online social networks (Stephen and Toubia, 2010). (Kacen, 1998) defines that social commerce is the extensive usage of social network technologies for e-commerce transactions and these technologies facilitate interactions among the people who want to purchase stuff. Meanwhile, there are two types of transactions such as offline and online, but online s-commerce is not totally different than offline and as well as online. In offline individuals not only for purchase stuff and for social interactions would be possible, moreover entertainment would be possible in it and it is also called 'retail therapy'. In case of online s-commerce, the social interaction takes place at different context with the help of internet. S-commerce will be discussed in broad and narrow view; in broad view in order to draw the attention of shopping behavior, consideration of product, buying intent, post purchase behavior and retention of individuals, marketers are influence the social media sites. In narrow view, Social commerce sites have been accelerated with the help of social media in the presence of Digital. Yadav et al. (2013) study defines that social commerce is an exchange related activity that are influenced on the individual's social network in the presence of a computer mediated environment. The study also points out that s-commerce exchange stages are stimulating the stages of buyer behavior.

Literature on usages of Social commerce

(Kuppuswamy & Narayan, 2010) reveals that s-commerce does not differ a lot with online or offline. The difference can discuss based on potential scale, reach, frequency, easy sharing and connecting process. Anderson et al. (2011) stated that the channels of social commerce are strongly influencing the behavior of clients. Thus, (Weijun, 2011) the business unit is more probable to satisfied customers since it capitalizes community to realize viciousness of internet sites, and quickly concentrate on targeted prospects leads to reduce the psychic energy. Wang et al. (2012) study conducted on 'the Evolution of Social Commerce: The People, Management, Technology

and Information Dimensions' a survey conducted with 292 participants. The study concentrates on how peer communication impact on purchasing of merchandise and online shopper socialization through social media and the results reveals that peer communication positively affected by conformity with peers to take the purchase decision. Vries et al. (2012) results indicated that the amount of likes on post positively associated with share of comments for buying decision; brand post quality improves if the brand post on the right place of the page can draw the attentions of viewers. Social commerce provides benefits for both customers and sellers at the same time, customers will make the selection based on date availability with the seller and from different customers. (Rad and Benyoucef, 2010) paper entitled 'A Model for Understanding Social Commerce', the paper highlights on the model of social interaction and involvement. The results found that different stages of purchase through social commerce influence on the user's interaction and involvement. (Curty & Zhang, 2011) study states that the success mantra of the organizations is to think in an empathetic way to understand the customer needs and satisfying those needs as desired by them via through social media channels.

Literature on Entrepreneurship taking advantage of S-commerce

There is no much studies relating to entrepreneurship and s-commerce but still it is a booming topic for the business development and both the areas are emerging topics in the modern era. Significantly, entrepreneurship is a vital entity because the economies of all countries across the world strongly depend on it. (Merriam-Webster, 2015) dictionary say that the intention of the entrepreneur is to create the opportunities for generating the revenue and risk; and works as an employee or worker; a person who starts a venture business, develops an idea (Burns, 2011). According to (Hisrich, 2011) entrepreneur is a person who takes a chance of perceiving an opportunity. The foremost responsibility of an entrepreneur is to design the business plan, check and execute the plan, find the gaps (deviations) and fill the gaps. to find the deviations. It is to note that the customers are the best source for the idea generation. The traditional media and modern media have been providing the opportunities in different aspects for the entrepreneurs. The traditional media offer only one-way experience for the betterment where as modern social media allow in two-way interactive experience. Social media will be acting as a facilitator for improving the interaction, opinions, and views & cross communication between customers and entrepreneurs. Hence, the researcher made a modest effort to choose the entrepreneurs based on the parameters like experience on selling and shopping, profit victimizers through social commerce.

3. Conceptual framework

According to (Shamare, 2014) social commerce is a related to the innovation of technology advancement. The present study has developed the conceptual framework based on the technological diffusion literature. Technology acceptance model (TAM) suggested by Davis's (1989); Fleischer, M & Tornatzky, L, G. (1990) focused on technological-organizational-environmental model (TOE);

Azjen, I. (1991) developed a framework on TBP such as Theory of Planned Behaviour; DOI framework focus on Diffusion aspects in Innovation Theory highlighted by Roger’s (1995);

There are some organizations will come under innovation diffusion and these firms basically use DOI and TOE model. According to (Salman, A et.al, 2014)to examine the automation process in the early phases of IT diffusion firms’ basically focus on user acceptance models like TAM and TPB. The present study improved and develops based on the user acceptance model and TAM model applied by many of the researchers to know the user acceptance and further the extension of TAM model is TPB model.

(Davis, 1989)examines two attributes such as Perceived usefulness and ease of use based on user acceptance model; the questions raised in this study are how and when the user decision impact based on new technology and a variety of things; it is to observe that two variable studied in this study,i.e perceived usefulness which means the degree of individual believes the employing a specific system would enhance individual job performance; perceived ease of use which means the degree of individual have a faith on the employing a specific structure would be free from effort. Hence, the researcher used perceived ease of use and usefulness attributes in the present study to evaluate entrepreneur’s attitude perception towards social commerce.

The above figure explains the context used in this paper to investigate the influence of social media on social commerce. The study discussed the present social commerce usage among peoples on social media and factors affecting on social commerce.

4. Objectives of the Study

- To examine the entrepreneur awareness and knowledge towards social commerce.
- To investigate the impact of social commerce on different business entrepreneurs.

5. Research Methodology

The primary data was collected from entrepreneurs through personal interview under survey method in Chittoor district. The researcher physically traveled with the help of ten MBA students to take the opinion from the respondent’s

location. In addition to this, ten MBA students trained as per questionnaire data collection and directed them to collect the data. The sample areas are confined Madanapalle, Chittoor and Tirupati towns in Chittoor district. In each town 50 respondents were participating for the study and total150 questionnaires distributed across the selected towns. The samples of 40, 43 and 42 questionnaires were finalized from three towns. The entrepreneurs were chosen based on purposive sampling in each selected town. The selected respondents who were already used, access, sell and purchase through social media. The respondents were considered who confined to use different applications like WhatsApp, Twitter, Facebook and Instagramfor doing selling and purchase. The sample was collected from entrepreneurs under the domains of apparels, accessories, gadgets, food, entertainment, photography, beauty & health services and repair works.

6. Result and Discussions

Table 1: Respondents’ Profile

		No. of Respondents	Percentage
Age	26-35	90	72
	36-45	19	15
	46-55	16	13
	Above 55	0	0
Gender	Male	94	75
	Female	31	25
Ethnicity	Local	100	80
	Non-local	25	20
Marital Status	Single	56	45
	Married	69	55
Education	SSC	15	12
	Intermediate/Diploma	30	24

	Graduate	65	52
	Post Graduate	15	12
	Total	125	100

Table 1 indicates that 72 percent of the respondents were 26-35 followed by 15 percent were 36-45 and 13 percent were 46-55 age groups. Most of the entrepreneurs were under young age group. 75 percent were male, and 25 percent were female respondents. 80 percent were local and only 20 percent respondents were non-local entrepreneurs. 55 percent were married, and 45 percent respondents were single as marital status. 52 percent were graduate followed by 24 percent were intermediate/diploma, SSC and PG were 12 percent each completed their education.

Table 2: Mode of Social Media usage

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Smart Phones	65	52
Computers	45	36
Both	15	12
Total	125	100

Table 2 provides that 52 percent was used smart phones, 36 percent was used computers and only 12 percent was used both modes for social media.

Table 3: Sources of Information for Social media awareness

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Newspaper/magazine	5	4
Radio/television	5	4

Table 4: Time consumed on social networking sites

Time spent for social networking sites	Facebook	WhatsApp	Twitter	Instagram
1-2 hours	15	11	42	26
3-5 hours	30	18	25	
6-7 hours	50	48		
More than 7 hours	5	21		

Table 4 depicts that social commerce transaction, 50 percent of the respondents have transacted between 6 to 7 hours over the last one year, followed by 30 percent 3 to 5 hours, 15 percent 1-2 hours and only 5 percent more than 7 hours; 48 percent of the respondents have transacted between 6 to 7 hours over the last one year, followed by 21 percent more than 7 hours, 18 percent 3 to 5 hours and 11 percent 1 to 2 hours respectively; 42 percent of the respondents have transacted only 1 to 2 hours and 25 percent 3 to 5 hours, respectively; only 26 percent respondents have transacted 1 to 2 hours respectively over the last one year. Surprisingly, the majority of the entrepreneurs are eagerly looking to buy and sell through online rather than physically.

Table 5: Frequently purchased items or services by customers

	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Apparels	84	67
Accessories	115	92
Gadgets	30	24
Food	51	41
Entertainment	32	26
Photography Services	73	58
Beauty & Health Services	45	36
Repair works	10	8

Internet	65	52
Social network	40	32
Family and friends	10	8
Total	125	100

Table 3 reveals that 52 percent respondents through the internet, 32 percent through social network, 8 percent through family & friends and 4 percent each through newspapers & television for source of awareness of social media usage. The study reveals that the respondent's level of awareness on social commerce towards selling online through social media is considerably moderate to high and most of respondents bought and sold through most trusted social network sites.

Out of 125 respondents, 120 or 96 percent people says that social commerce is a part of their daily lives, indicates that social commerce dealings with respect of business are not new for the entrepreneurs and it would be getting awareness on social commerce gradually increasing. Almost 100 percent of the respondents were spending their time with Facebook account, 98 percent have spent on time with WhatsApp, 67 percent were spent their time with a twitter account, and only 38 percent have Instagram. Most of the entrepreneurs (72 percent) are frequently checking their social networking site to know for current updates of viewers on business.

Table 5 reveals that majority of the respondents purchased accessories, followed by apparels, photography services, food, beauty & health services, entertainment, gadgets and repair works. Hence it is found that many of the respondents are interested to buy online but they are often through offline if they found cheaper. Hence the above table clearly mention that many of the respondents frequently purchased apparels followed by accessories and photography services.

7. Entrepreneurs' intensions on Social commerce

Most of the respondents opined that social networking sites are appealing, easy to use, and combined form of images, videos and permit these for user's comment. Entrepreneurs in Chittoor district perceived that social commerce is very useful tool for buying and selling of items and at the same time they reveal that some of the sites create temptation and force for window shopping and unplanned purchases. Few of the people opined that social commerce usage were more time consuming and its effects negatively on their regular activities. Social network sites can be used for time pass or whenever feel bored or stressed they may use it for relaxing. Some social network sites are creating fascinating and providing cheaper price towards goods/services. In addition, 65 percent of the entrepreneurs says that technology up gradation is not up to

the standard and it's still at beginning stage. Hence, most of the entrepreneurs say that governing bodies must develop technology up gradation which permits future expansion of social commerce in Chittoor district.

8. Conclusion

From the results and analysis, the study was focused on 125 entrepreneurs lived in Tirupati, Madanapalle & Chittoor town who considered social media as a model for doing business. The study found that 52 percent were using smart phones, 36 percent were using computers and only 12 percent were using both modes for social media. In terms of information

sources, the respondents gaining through the internet and social networking. Almost 100 percent of the respondents were spending their time with Facebook account, 98 percent have spent on time with WhatsApp, 67 percent were spent their time with twitter account, and only 38 percent have Instagram. Most of the entrepreneurs (72 percent) are frequently checking their social networking site to know for current updates of viewers on business and many of the entrepreneurs are eagerly looking to buy and sell through online rather than physically. Many of the respondents frequently purchased apparels followed by accessories and photography services.

References

- Ahlqvist T, Back A, Halonen M, Heinonen S (2010). Social Media Roadmaps Exploring the Futures Triggered by Social Media, VTT Research Notes 2454. Available from: <http://www.vtt.fi/inf/pdf/tiedotteet/2008/T2454.pdf>.
- Anderson M, Sims J, Price J, Brusa J (2011). Social Media Emerges as a Commerce Channel. Booz & Company Inc.
- Azjen I (1991). The Theory of Planned Behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes* 50, 179-211.
- Boyd DM, Ellison NB (2007). Social network sites: Definition, history, and scholarship. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 13(1), 210–230.
- Boyd D (2007). Why youth (heart) social network sites: The role of networked publics in teenage social life. In: Buckingham D (ed) *MacArthur Foundation Series on Digital Learning: Youth, Identity, and Digital Media Volume*. MIT Press, Cambridge, MA.
- Burns P (2010). **Entrepreneurship and Small Business**. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Cecere L, Owyang J, Li C, Etlinger S, Tran C (2010). *Rise of Social Commerce: A Trail Guide for the Social Commerce Pioneer*. Altimeter Group Publication.
- Chen Y, Fay S, Wang Q (2011). The Role of Marketing in Social Media: How Online Customer Reviews Evolve. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 25(2), 85-94.
- Chen Y, Wang Q, Xie J (2011). Online Social Interactions: A Natural Experiment on Word of Mouth versus Observational Learning. *Journal of Marketing*, 238-254.
- Curdy RG, Zhang P (2011). Social Commerce: Looking Back and Forward. Paper presented at the American Society for Information Science and Technology. New Orleans, LA, USA.
- Davis FD (1989). Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use and User Acceptance of Information Technology. *MIS Quarterly* 13(3), 319-340.
- Hashim NA, Abdullah N (2014). Catastrophe of E-Commerce among Malaysian SMEs - Between Its Perceived and Proven Benefits. *Journal Pengurusan*, 42, 13-41.
- Hensel K, Deis MH (2010). Using Social Media to Increase Advertising and Improve Marketing. *The Entrepreneurial Executive*, 15, 87-97.
- Hisrich RD (2011). *Entrepreneurship*. McGraw-Hill Education. ISBN 978-0-07062-017-9.
- Hoffman DF, Novak TP (2012). Why Do People Use Social Media? Empirical Findings and a New Theoretical Framework for Social Media Goal Pursuit. Available from: SSRN: <http://ssrn.com/abstract=1989586> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1989586>.
- Hussain AH, Bohari AM (2012). The Use of High-Speed Internet as a Platform for Compulsive Online Buying: A Case of Study of Post-graduate Students in Malaysia. *Geografia-Journal of Society and Space*, 8 (7), 32 – 43.
- Infographics (2014) [Cited 20 October 2014]. Available from: <http://socialmarketingwriting.com/tipssharing-infographic-facebook-twitter-pinterest-linkedin/>.
- International Telecommunication Union - ITU (2010) The rise of social networking – Changing the Web as we know it. [Cited 20 Oct 2014]. Available from: <http://www.itu.int/net/itunews/issues/2010/06/35.aspx>.
- Kaplan AM, Haenlein M (2010) Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of social media. *Business Horizons* 53(1), 59-68. doi:10.1016/j.bushor.2009.09.003.
- Kirschner PA, Karpinski AC (2010). Facebook and academic performance. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 26, 1237-1245.
- Kuppuswamy S, Narayan P (2010). The Impact of Social Networking Websites on the Education of Youth, *International Journal of Virtual Communities and Social Networking*, 2(1), 67-79.
- Marsden P (2011). F-Commerce Selling on Facebook: The Opportunity for Consumer Brands. Available from: http://socialcommercetoday.com/documents/Szygy_2011.pdf.
- Moran M, Seaman J, Tinti-Kane H (2011). Teaching, Learning, and Sharing: How Today's Higher Education Faculty Use Social Media, Pearson Learning Solutions and Babson Survey Research Group, Pearson Learning Solutions.
- Nicholson S (2011). Infographics: The history of online social networking [Cited 17 April 2011]. Available from: <http://socialmediatoday.com/socmedsean/286629/infographic-history-online-socialnetworking>.
- Rad A, Benyoucef M (2010). A Model for Understanding Social Commerce. *Information Systems Journal* 4 (2), 1-11.
- Rogers EM (1995). *Diffusion of Innovations*. 4th ed. Free Press, New York.
- Salman A, Mohamed Salleh MA, Abdullah MY, Mustafa N, Ahmad AL, Chang PK, Saad S (2014) ICT Acceptance among Malaysian Urbanites: A Study of Additional Variable in User Acceptance of the New Media. *Geografia-Journal of Society and Space* 10 (6), 86 – 963.
- Stephen AT, Toubia O (2010). Deriving Value from Social Commerce Networks. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 47(2), 215-228.
- Tornatzky LG, Fleischer, M (1990). *The Process of Technological Innovation*. Lexington Books, Massachusetts.
- Turban E, King D, Lee J, Liang TP, Deborrah C (2012). *Electronic Commerce 2012: A Managerial and Social Networks Perspective*. Pearson Prentice Hall.

31. Vries LD, Gensler S, Leeflang PSH (2012). Popularity of Brand Posts on Brand Fan Pages: An Investigation of the Effects of Social Media Marketing. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 26, 83–91.
32. Wang C, Zhang P (2012). The Evolution of Social Commerce: The People, Management, Technology and Information Dimensions. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 31(5), 105-127.
33. Weijun W, Lin L (2011) Research on Social Commerce in Web2.0 Environment. Paper presented at the International Conference on E -Business and E - Government (ICEE), Shanghai, China.
34. Zimmerman J, Ng D (2012). Social Media Marketing All-in-One for Dummies. For Dummies Publisher.
35. <http://www.myjournal.my/public/browse.php>